

New spectrophotometric methods for the simultaneous determination of amlodipine and ramipril

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Abstract : Three new analytical methods were developed based on the simultaneous estimation of drugs in a binary mixture without prior separation of amlodipine and ramipril. Quantitative estimation of these drugs in marketed brands of the tablets was carried out using first order derivative, simultaneous equations and multi wavelength methods. Amlodipine and ramipril have absorbance maxima at 360 nm and 206.5 nm respectively in methanol. Both the drugs obey Beer's law in the concentration range employed for these methods. The results of analysis have been validated statistically and also by recovery studies.

Keywords : Ramipril, amlodipine.

Introduction

Amlodipine besylate is calcium antagonist and chemically, it is 3-ethyl-5-methyl-(4RS)-2-[(2-aminoethoxy)methyl]-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate benzene sulphonate. The British Pharmacopoeia examines amlodipine besylate by liquid chromatography. HPLC¹, reversed phase HPLC², colorimetric method³⁻⁵, HPTLC^{6,7}, gas liquid chromatography⁸, difference spectrophotometric estimation⁹ are few of the methods reported in literature for the simultaneous analysis of amlodipine besylate with various drugs from their respective formulations. Ramipril is a long acting angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor used as an anti hypertensive drug. A survey of the literature revealed that HPLC¹⁰, atomic absorption spectrophotometry¹¹ and capillary electrophoresis¹² methods have been reported for the estimation of ramipril in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Although amlodipine and ramipril are commonly used in dual drug therapy as a potent anti hypertensive drug, yet no method is so far reported for their simultaneous estimation. A successful attempt has been made to estimate these two drugs simultaneously by spectrophotometric method.

Results and discussion

Method I : Employing first derivative method :

Upon examining the first-derivative spectra of the two drugs, it can be noticed that amlodipine can be determined at 249.5 nm where ramipril has no contribution and ramipril can be determined at 211.5 nm where amlodipine shows a zero crossing.

$$A = -0.0016C + 0.0002 \quad r = 0.9994 \\ (\lambda = 249.5 \text{ nm}) \quad (1)$$

$$A = -0.0014C + 0.0009 \quad r = 0.9981 \\ (\lambda = 211.5 \text{ nm}) \quad (2)$$

where C is the concentration in $\mu\text{g/mL}$, A is the peak amplitude of the first-derivative curves at 249.5 and 211.5 nm for amlodipine and ramipril respectively and r is the correlation coefficient.

The selectivity of the proposed procedure was examined by determining the recovery of the two drugs in laboratory-prepared mixtures containing different ratios of the two drugs and satisfactory results were obtained (Table 1).

The proposed procedure was also applied for the determination of amlodipine and ramipril in the marketed tablets (Table 2). The validity of the method was further assessed by applying the standard addition technique (Table 3). Statistical analysis was carried out by the official software SPSS.

Table 1. Results of analysis of amlodipine and ramipril in the laboratory prepared mixtures

Sample no.	Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)		Recovery ^a (%)					
			Derivaive spectrophotometry		Simultaneous equation method		Multi wavelength method	
			Amlo	Rami	Amlo	Rami	Amlo	Rami
1	25	0	99.50	-	99.20	-	98.80	-
2	20	5	98.96	99.35	99.32	100.01	99.78	99.69
3	15	10	99.25	100.14	98.71	99.87	98.15	100.12
4	10	15	98.23	99.14	98.65	99.87	98.15	98.36
5	5	20	100.23	100.93	100.12	99.23	99.62	99.65
6	0	25	-	99.94	-	98.97	-	99.96
Mean			99.23	99.90	99.20	99.47	99.24	99.56
Standard deviation			0.83	0.53	0.23	0.12	0.98	0.20

^aEach reading is an average of nine determinations.

Amlo : Amlodipine, Rami : Ramipril.

Statistical calculations were carried out by the SPSS (official software).

Table 2. Determination of amlodipine and ramipril in tablets using the proposed methods

Tablet brand	Recovery(%) ±SD ^a					
	First-derivative spectrophotometry		Simultaneous equation method		Multi wavelength method	
	Amlo	Rami	Amlo	Rami	Amlo	Rami
A	99.88 ± 0.001	99.68 ± 0.006	98.77 ± 0.040	100.06 ± 0.015	99.21 ± 0.040	100.02 ± 0.030
B	99.63 ± 0.001	99.93 ± 0.002	99.01 ± 0.038	99.29 ± 0.014	99.01 ± 0.026	99.89 ± 0.051

^aEach reading is an average of nine determinations.

Amlo : Amlodipine, Rami : Ramipril.

Table 3. Compilation of results of drug recovery study

Method	Tablet brand	Percent recovery ±SD ^a	
		Amlo	Rami
I	A	100.50 ± 0.23	99.84 ± 0.05
	B	99.89 ± 0.08	99.87 ± 0.09
II	A	100.10 ± 0.33	100.35 ± 0.22
	B	99.96 ± 0.08	99.85 ± 0.13
III	A	99.24 ± 0.56	99.54 ± 0.69
	B	99.04 ± 0.90	98.89 ± 0.64

^aEach reading is an average of nine determinations.

Amlo : Amlodipine, Rami : Ramipril.

Method II : Employing simultaneous equations method :

This method of analysis is based on the absorption of drugs (X and Y) at the wavelength maximum of the other. The quantification analysis of amlodipine and ramipril in a binary mixture were performed with the following equations :

$$Cx = (A_2ay_1 - A_1ay_2)/ax_2ay_1 - ax_1ay_2 \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$Cy = (A_1ax_2 - A_2ax_1)/ax_2ay_1 - ax_1ay_2 \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

where C_x and C_y are the concentrations of X and Y respectively in the diluted sample, ax₁ and ax₂ are absorptivities of X at λ₁ and λ₂, ay₁ and ay₂ are absorptivities of Y at λ₁ and λ₂. The absorbance of the diluted samples at λ₁ and λ₂ are A₁ and A₂ respectively.

On the basis of above equations two simultaneous equations were formed for the estimation of amlodipine and ramipril (Fig. 1).

$$A_1 = 403.9C_{\text{ramipril}} + 51730C_{\text{amlodipine}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{206.5}) \quad (3)$$

$$A_2 = 127.72C_{\text{amlodipine}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{360}) \quad (4)$$

where A₁, A₂ are absorbance of the mixture at 206.5 nm and 360 nm respectively. 403.90 is absorptivity of ramipril at 206.5 nm, 517.30 and 127.72 are the absorptivities of amlodipine at 206.5 nm and 360 nm respectively. Solving these two equations C_{ramipril} (concentration of ramipril) and C_{amlodipine} (concentration of the amlodipine) can be readily found out.

Fig. 1. Overlain spectrum of amlodipine (AM) and ramipril (RP).

Method III : Multiwavelength method :

The utility of multiwavelength data processing programme is to calculate the unknown concentration of component of interest present in a mixture containing both a component of interest and an unwanted interfering component by the mechanism of the absorbance difference between two points on the spectra of the mixture is directly proportional to the concentration of the components of interest, independent of the interfering components. It involves the estimation of two components, each time considering the second one to be an interfering one. An important criterion for this method is the presence of some absorbance in the spectrum of interfering component. The measuring wavelength can be spaced either equally or arbitrarily, depending on the measuring purpose.

Two wavelengths were selected 223.5 nm and 232.5 nm for the ramipril at which amlodipine shows the equal absorbance and 360 nm for amlodipine at which ramipril shows no absorbance.

Two equations were formed

$$A_1 = 0.0066C_{\text{ramipril}} + 0.0081 \quad (5)$$

$$A_2 = 0.0121C_{\text{amlodipine}} + 0.0085 \quad (6)$$

where A_1 is absorbance difference between the 232.5 nm and 223.5 nm and A_2 is the absorbance at 360 nm for ramipril and amlodipine respectively.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Shimadzu 1700 Pharmaspec UV-Visible spectrophotometer with a matched pair of 10 mm quartz cells was used. Amlodipine received as gift sample from Ranbaxy Labs. and ramipril Cipla Labs. were used as such without further purification. Methanol, A.R. grade (Merck, India Limited, Mumbai) was used in the study. The commercially available marketed tablet containing a combination of amlodipine 2.5 mg and ramipril 2.5 mg were procured from local pharmacy.

Preparation of standard stock solution :

Amlodipine and ramipril (100 mg) were accurately weighed and dissolved separately in 100 mL of methanol to give stock solutions (1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Aliquots of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ solution were suitably diluted with methanol to give final concentrations.

Absorbance was measured at 360 nm and 206.5 nm for amlodipine and ramipril respectively. The zero and first order derivative absorption spectra were recorded. The peak amplitude of the obtained first-derivative spectra was measured at 249.5 and 211.5 nm for amlodipine and ramipril respectively.

Procedure for analysis of tablet formulation :

Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and powdered. A quantity of powder equivalent to 2.5 mg amlodipine and 2.5 mg ramipril was transferred in 100 mL volumetric flask, shaken thoroughly with 50 mL methanol and

filtered. The filtrate was further diluted with methanol as in standard solution preparation. Different aliquots of solutions were taken and analyzed by using the procedures described earlier. The peak amplitude of the first-derivative spectra was measured at 249.5 and 211.5 nm for amlodipine and ramipril, respectively. The amount of the two drugs was calculated from the computed regression equations or from the suggested simultaneous equation and multiwavelength method. The results are represented in Table 2.

Recovery studies :

Accuracy of the method was checked by recovery studies, wherein sample was spiked with known quantity of standard drug of amlodipine and ramipril at different levels. The percentage recovery was found to be between 99.04–100.50 and 98.89–100.35 for amlodipine and ramipril respectively. Standard addition technique was applied for assessing the validity of the suggested methods (Table 3).

Conclusion :

The main advantage of the proposed method is its suitability for routine determination of amlodipine and ramipril from their marketed formulations. The proposed methods are economic, simple, sensitive, precise and reproducible and do not require any expensive or sophisticated apparatus, in contrast with the reported chromatographic methods. These methods are simple, accurate and rapid, and they require no preliminary separation and can therefore be used for routine analysis of both drugs in quality control laboratories.

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